

ISic0136

I.Sicily inscription 0136

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico
Baldassare Romano

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. C(ai) Audi · Veri

2. loco cub · in

3. agr(um) ped(es) XXII

4. in [f]r(ontem) ped(es) XXII

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini

Translation (en)

(This is the funerary stone) of Gaius Audius Verius, his resting place (measuring)
22 feet long by 22 feet wide.

Commentary

This appears to be the only attestation of loco cub(---)

; Mommsen suggests to undersand as loco cub(andi patente)

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Digital identifiers:

TM 285123

EDR 111016

EDCS 22100080

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7379 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650798>)

Bivona, L. 1994. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del museo civico di Termini Imerese. *Kokalos Supplementi / Sikelika serie storica*. Palermo / Rome. At 55

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